

Buffer gas cooling of a continuous CO molecular beam

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Abstract: We characterise a new continuous buffer gas cooled source using CO molecules. We show results about the source performance considering different parameters, like gas flow rate, nozzle size, and internal cell volume. The beam contains 2.5×10^{14} molecules/(s sr) at about 160 m/s. Moreover, for two rotational states we observe an unexpected population distribution that we tentatively attribute to a lower temperature inside the cell. Considering the importance of buffer-gas cooling for experiments on ultracold molecules prepared with direct laser cooling, we believe that our work will improve this key first-stage cooling, accelerating the adoption of molecules in the framework of quantum technologies.

1. Introduction

Ultracold molecules are very promising candidates for advancing modern physics, with applications ranging from fundamental physics to frontier technologies such as quantum simulation and quantum computation [1, 2]. This is due to their rich internal structure, symmetry, and strong intramolecular fields, which make them ideal systems for investigating new physics. However, this same complexity poses significant challenges for cooling and detection, making these processes much more difficult compared to atoms. To overcome these difficulties, a first cooling stage is usually applied to the molecular sample. Virtually all current experiments with laser-cooled molecules rely on a buffer gas source [3, 4]. In this source, molecules are injected or produced inside the cell, where they thermalise with a cold rare buffer gas, typically helium or neon. The molecular beam exiting the source is usually in an intermediate regime between effusive and hydrodynamic, i.e. experiencing almost no or a few collisions, respectively, at the exit aperture.

Buffer gas cooling techniques have been successfully applied to a variety of species, spanning a broad spectrum of chemical properties, including alkali atoms [5, 6], alkaline earths [7], metals [8], chemically reactive polar molecules [9–11], and polyatomic molecules [12].

In this work, we present our newly-developed buffer gas source that we characterize using carbon monoxide. Although CO is not a particularly interesting species for laser cooling, it has the advantage of being easily available in a bottle. Moreover, by exciting CO to its first excited, metastable, electronic state, the $a^3\Pi$ state, characterisation of the beam is straightforward. With the present setup for a continuously seeded buffer gas beam, we can calculate the overall efficiency of the source from the known amount of gas that we let into the system and the number of cold molecules in the beam. Such measurements are extremely hard when the species of interest are produced via laser ablation and/or chemical reaction. Intense effusive beams can be

47 produced with other molecules, too, [7] but CO is particularly advantageous given its relatively
 48 low freezing temperature.

49 We optimized the source for maximal flux and minimal velocity of the molecular beam trying
 50 various combinations of nozzle sizes and cell lengths. We also measure molecules in two different
 51 rotational states in order to estimate rotational thermalization inside the cell and provide an
 52 estimation of the beam temperature.

53 2. Theoretical description of the dynamics within a buffer gas cell

54 Buffer-gas cooling of atoms or molecules relies on collisions with cold buffer gas atoms at
 55 cryogenic temperatures, bringing the target species to low temperatures. The buffer gas dissipates
 56 the translational and internal energy of the target species, ideally without chemical reaction or
 57 cluster formation. This method of energy dissipation is independent of any specific energy level
 58 structure, making it applicable to a wide range of target species [7].

59 A comprehensive overview of the dynamics in a buffer gas cell can be found in Refs. [4, 9].
 60 Here, we focus on outlining the key parameters associated with our setup.

61 Consider a buffer gas cell with a volume defined by $V_{\text{cell}} = A_{\text{cell}} \times L_c$, where L_c is the length
 62 of the cell interior and A_{cell} is the cross-sectional area. Typically, L_c is of the order of a few
 63 centimeters, and A_{cell} of a few cm^2 . The cell is maintained at a fixed temperature T by a cryogenic
 64 refrigerator, typically between 1 K and 20 K. We use helium as buffer gas.

65 Buffer Gas Flow through the cell

66 The buffer gas exits the cell through a round aperture with diameter d_{aperture} of a few millimeters.
 67 The flow rate of the buffer gas, He in our case, is typically measured in standard cubic centimeters
 68 per minute (SCCM), where 1 SCCM is approximately equivalent to a flow of 4.5×10^{17} gas
 69 particles per second. Under steady-state conditions, the number density of helium atoms in the
 70 buffer cell, n_{He} , can be estimated by considering the constant flow of helium into the cell, f_{He} ,
 71 and the pumping speed through the aperture [4],

$$n_{\text{He}} = \frac{4 f_{\text{He}}}{A_{\text{aperture}} \bar{v}_{\text{He}}}, \quad (1)$$

72 where \bar{v}_{He} is the mean thermal velocity of the helium atoms near the aperture. For a typical flow
 73 of 1 SCCM of helium through an aperture with a diameter of 3 mm in a buffer cell maintained
 74 at a temperature of around 4 K, the number density is $n_{\text{He}} \approx 2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The properties of
 75 the target species emerging from the buffer cell are solely determined by collisions with the
 76 buffer gas, which can be quantified by the mean free path. The mean free path is defined as
 77 $\lambda_{\text{CO}} = 1/(n_{\text{He}} \sigma_{\text{CO-He}} \sqrt{m_{\text{CO}}/m_{\text{He}} + 1})$, where σ is a collisional cross section and m a mass. To a
 78 good approximation [9], $\sigma_{\text{CO-He}} \approx \sigma_{\text{He-He}}$ and $\sigma_{\text{He-He}} \sim 10^{-14} \text{ cm}^2$ [13].

79 The Reynolds number (Re) is an important figure of merit for the description of a gas flow.
 80 For the buffer gas flows through an aperture of diameter d_{aperture} , the Reynolds number can be
 81 approximated as,

$$\text{Re} \approx \frac{2 d_{\text{aperture}}}{\lambda_{\text{He}}}, \quad (2)$$

82 where λ_{He} is the mean free path for the collisions of buffer gas atoms and it is expressed as,
 83 $\lambda_{\text{He}} = 1/(\sqrt{2} n_{\text{He}} \sigma_{\text{He-He}})$. Therefore, the Reynolds number can be expressed as,

$$\text{Re} \approx \frac{8\sqrt{2} f_{\text{He}} \sigma_{\text{He-He}}}{\pi d_{\text{aperture}} \bar{v}_{\text{He}}}. \quad (3)$$

84 The flow regimes can be categorised into three distinct types based on the Reynolds number,
 85 which reflects the extent of collisional interactions near the cell aperture. In the effusive regime

86 ($\text{Re} \lesssim 1$), few or no collisions occur near the aperture, and the beam properties align with the
 87 thermal distribution inside the cell. Moving into the intermediate or partially-hydrodynamic
 88 regime ($1 \lesssim \text{Re} \lesssim 100$), collisions begin to influence the beam properties, although the flow does
 89 not yet exhibit fully fluid-like characteristics. Finally, in the hydrodynamic regime ($\text{Re} \gtrsim 100$),
 90 the buffer gas behaves like a fluid, and the beam properties start to resemble those of a supersonic
 91 expansion, leading to a colder and less divergent beam.

92 Extraction efficiency of the cell

93 The particles of the target species can be depleted from the cooling region of the buffer cell
 94 through two primary processes: diffusion and entrainment. In the diffusion process, a significant
 95 fraction of particles may collide with, and adhere to, the walls of the cell, while only a very small
 96 fraction diffuse out through the aperture. The effectiveness of diffusion through the aperture is
 97 governed by the ratio of the aperture area to the surface area of the cooling region, which is
 98 typically $\leq 1\%$. Consequently, for the remainder of this discussion, we assume that the diffusion
 99 process predominantly results in particle losses, thereby limiting the extraction efficiency of
 100 particles from the buffer gas cell. In contrast, the second process involves entrainment, where
 101 particles are extracted or “pumped out” by the helium flow continuously emerging through the
 102 aperture.

103 Considering the diffusion and the entrainment processes, we define two characteristic time
 104 scales for particle movement within the cell. The diffusion time scale, τ_{diff} , represents the time
 105 required for particles of the target species to diffuse to the walls of the cooling region. The
 106 pump-out time scale, τ_{pump} , represents the time it takes for these particles to traverse the cell
 107 under the influence of helium flow. Following Ref. [4], we can write

$$\tau_{\text{diff}} = \frac{16 A_{\text{cell}} n_{\text{He}} \sigma_{\text{CO-He}}}{9 \pi \bar{v}_{\text{He}}}. \quad (4)$$

108 and

$$\tau_{\text{pump}} = \frac{4 V_{\text{cell}}}{\bar{v}_{\text{He}} A_{\text{aperture}}} \quad (5)$$

109 The diffusion and pump-out times are typically around 1–10 ms. The efficiency of particle
 110 extraction from the cell is governed by the interplay between these two time scales. Therefore, it
 111 is instructive to define a dimensionless parameter

$$\gamma_{\text{cell}} \equiv \frac{\tau_{\text{diff}}}{\tau_{\text{pump}}} = \frac{4}{9\pi} \frac{n_{\text{He}} \sigma_{\text{CO-He}} A_{\text{aperture}}}{L_{\text{cell}}} \approx \frac{\sigma_{\text{CO-He}} f_{\text{He}}}{L_{\text{cell}} \bar{v}_{\text{He}}}. \quad (6)$$

112 The value of γ_{cell} defines the regime of particle extraction. For instance, $\gamma_{\text{cell}} \lesssim 1$ corresponds to
 113 the “diffusion limit”, where particles diffuse to the wall faster than they are extracted from the
 114 cell. This regime results in a low output flux of target particles. In contrast, when $\gamma_{\text{cell}} > 1$, the
 115 system operates in the “hydrodynamic regime”, resulting in a beam rich in target species.

116 While γ_{cell} can estimate the extraction efficiency well, there are instances where this simple
 117 estimate breaks down. For example, γ_{cell} has no explicit dependence on the aperture diameter;
 118 however, it has been observed experimentally that decreasing the cell aperture diameter can
 119 reduce the extraction efficiency. [14, 15] These measurements suggest that the cell aperture
 120 diameter should not be too small (less than 3 mm) to achieve good extraction. It is thus helpful
 121 to determine empirically the optimal cell geometry. The gas flow regime, described by the Reynolds
 122 number, Eq. (3), and the extraction parameter γ_{cell} , Eq. (6) are related by a factor that depends on
 123 geometry:

$$\frac{\gamma_{\text{cell}}}{\text{Re}} \propto \frac{d_{\text{aperture}}}{L_{\text{cell}}}. \quad (7)$$

124 This means that, at least in principle, it is possible to separately control the extraction efficiency
 125 (governed by γ_{cell}) and the flow regime (governed by Re). Most buffer gas sources operate in
 126 either the effusive or the intermediate flow regimes, and it is experimentally challenging to design
 127 a beam that is completely effusive, has good extraction, and has sufficient thermalization.

128 Thermalization of CO molecules

129 As previously mentioned, the characteristics of the target particles emerging from the buffer cell
 130 are determined by the collisions with buffer gas atoms. The translational temperature of the CO
 131 molecules, T_{CO} , after undergoing N collisions with the buffer gas, can be estimated as follows [4],

$$\frac{T_{\text{CO}}(N)}{T_{\text{He}}} \approx 1 + \frac{T_{\text{CO}}(0)}{T_{\text{He}}} e^{-N/\kappa}, \quad (8)$$

132 where $\kappa = (m_{\text{CO}} + m_{\text{He}})^2 / (2 m_{\text{CO}} m_{\text{He}})$, T_{He} is the temperature of the buffer gas atoms in the
 133 cell, ~ 4 K, and $T_{\text{CO}}(0)$ is the temperature of the target particles when they are introduced
 134 into the cell, ~ 70 K (see below). Using this formula, we estimate that for CO molecules in
 135 the buffer cell, about 30 collisions are needed to translationally cool the molecules from room
 136 temperature to within 2.5% of the temperature of the buffer gas atoms. For typical values of
 137 $\sigma_{\text{CO-He}} \approx 10^{-14}$ cm² and He number density of 10^{15-16} /cm³, the mean free path is 0.01 – 0.2 mm.
 138 Therefore, the thermalization length for the species in the buffer gas cell is typically no more
 139 than 30×0.2 mm = 6 mm.

140 Apart from translational cooling of the target species, buffer gas cooling is also effective
 141 at rotational quenching which is driven by the anisotropy of the helium interaction with the
 142 molecule [16]. Typical rotational relaxation cross sections for molecules with helium buffer gas
 143 are of the order $\sigma_{\text{rot}} \sim 10^{-(15-16)}$ cm² [17], which means that around $\sigma_{\text{CO-He}}/\sigma_{\text{rot}} \sim 10 - 100$
 144 collisions are required to relax a rotational state. With the parameters given above, we estimate
 145 that a cell length of 9–90 mm is required for full rotational quenching.

146 Forward Velocity of the CO beam

147 In the intermediate regime, the average velocity of the Helium, \bar{v}_{He} , is higher than that of CO,
 148 \bar{v}_{CO} , by a factor of $\sqrt{m_{\text{CO}}/m_{\text{He}}}$. The collisions of the Helium atoms with the CO near the aperture
 149 are predominantly in the forward direction. Therefore, the CO molecules are accelerated in the
 150 forward direction, which results in a velocity larger than the thermal velocity of the CO molecules
 151 in the cell.

152 CO molecules undergo approximately $\frac{Re}{2}$ collisions near the aperture [14]. For a small number
 153 of collisions, the resulting forward velocity is given by [4],

$$v_{\text{CO}} \approx \bar{v}_{\text{CO}} + 0.6 \bar{v}_{\text{He}} Re \frac{m_{\text{He}}}{m_{\text{CO}}} \quad (9)$$

154 This suggests a linear increase of forward velocity with Re ($1 \lesssim Re \lesssim 10$) and therefore with
 155 buffer gas flow. However, as v_{CO} approaches \bar{v}_{He} , the above model breaks down, as the maximum
 156 possible forward velocity of the CO molecules is $1.4\bar{v}_{\text{He}}$ as determined by the fully hydrodynamic
 157 expansions of the helium atoms [4]. We therefore expect that the forward velocity should saturate
 158 to this value at large enough Re . For $Re \gtrsim 10$, the forward velocity is described by the “sudden
 159 freeze” model,

$$v_{\text{CO}}(Re) \approx 1.4\bar{v}_{\text{He}} \left(1 - \frac{4}{Re^{4/5}}\right) \quad (10)$$

160 The transition to sudden-freeze model occurs at the flow rate for which there are collisions at a
 161 distance larger than one aperture diameter from the aperture. This happens for $Re \gtrsim 10$ [14]. For
 162 sufficiently high Re (specifically $Re \gtrsim 100$), species can achieve a forward velocity of

$$v_{\text{CO}} \approx 1.4\bar{v}_{\text{He}} \quad (11)$$

163 **3. Experimental system**

164 A schematic of the vacuum system is shown in Fig. 1. The vacuum system consists of two
165 chambers. The first chamber contains the buffer gas cell, which is connected to a two-stage
166 pulse tube cryostat (PT425, Cryomech). The second chamber houses the detection region. Both
167 chambers are pumped by turbo-molecular pumps, HiPace 1200 and HiPace 300 (Pfeiffer Vacuum),
168 for the first and second chamber, respectively. The system typically operates at a pressure of
169 approximately $\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar, which limits the number of collisions with background gas, thereby
170 facilitating the formation of a molecular beam. The pressure is measured in both chambers at the
171 room-temperature part of the chambers.

Fig. 1. Overview of the overall vacuum system (a) and a detailed arrangement of the buffer cell (b). Charcoal grains are glued to copper fins (as described in the text) and attached to a 4K cold head. For the visual clarity, only one of the charcoal fin arrangement is shown, on two different sides in the two pictures to avoid obstructing the view of the cell. The bottom of the radiation shield is closed by a series of copper stripes arranged in a chevron shape.

172 An aluminum shield is mounted in contact with the 40-K stage of the cryostat, while the buffer
173 cell is attached to the 4-K stage. The aluminum shield functions as a radiation shield, effectively
174 reducing the thermal radiation load on the buffer cell. A ~ 23 mm hole at the front of the radiation
175 shield serves as an aperture for the molecular beam to emerge. Additionally, two orthogonal
176 ports on the radiation shield, positioned perpendicular to the molecular beam, provide access for
177 the excitation laser. The excitation laser intercepts the molecular beam approximately 30 mm
178 after the cell nozzle. To further minimize the thermal load on the buffer cell, the radiation shield
179 is wrapped 10 layers of polyester foil, double-sided aluminized, perforated and interleaved with
180 10 layers of non-woven polyester spacer material.

181 Charcoal at cryogenic temperatures is well known for its ability to efficiently absorb helium. [18]
182 In many cryogenic buffer gas beam sources, the cell is surrounded by a small metal enclosure
183 maintained at 4K, with charcoal glued on its interior walls. Instead, we developed a skeletal
184 like copper structure mounted to the 4K head of the cryostat. Fine charcoal grains are glued
185 to the copper fins using a thin layer of thermally conductive epoxy glue. These fins are then
186 integrated into the copper framework, which is connected to the 4K cold head. This solution
187 substantially increases the area covered by charcoal, thereby enhancing helium pumping capacity,

188 while maintaining good conductance toward the turbo pump. The large copper surface covered
189 by charcoals allows for continuous pumping of 20 SCCM of Helium for over 2 days without
190 using the turbo pump before heating the system to release the adsorbed helium, a value much
191 higher compared to other systems.

192 3.1. Design of the buffer gas cell

193 The schematic of the buffer gas cell is shown in Fig. 2. The top part of the cell is attached to the
194 4K cold head of the cryostat. The cell is machined from a copper block and features a cylindrical
195 region, which we refer to as the “cooling region”. The temperature measured at the cell under
196 normal operation conditions is of 3.7 K.

Fig. 2. The cross-sectional view of the buffer cell illustrates the arrangement of the aperture and the gas inlet tubes for CO and helium. A polyether ether ketone (PEEK) component is employed to thermally isolate the CO inlet tube from the cold buffer cell, as described in the text. Furthermore, a cylindrical PEEK piece is integrated to precisely control the length of the cooling region. The temperature of the CO tube near the buffer cell is regulated using a cartridge heater mounted on a copper element.

197 The nozzle of the cell is machined from a separate copper piece and subsequently attached to
198 the buffer cell with a specific threading, facilitating a systematic study of how aperture dimensions
199 determine the system performance. The cooling region is designed as a cylinder with a diameter
200 of 15 mm. The exit nozzle has a conical shape, as outlined in [19]. The gas inlet configuration
201 for the buffer cell is depicted in Fig. 2. To precisely control the cooling region length, cylindrical
202 PEEK pieces are attached to the back end of the cell. These PEEK pieces feature appropriately
203 sized holes to allow helium flow into the cooling region, as shown in Fig. 2. By incorporating
204 these pieces, we reduced the overall length of the cell, allowing for controlled variation of the
205 cooling region length. In this study, we tested nozzles with diameters of 2, 3, 4, and 5 mm, and
206 cooling region lengths of 2, 3, 4, and 5 cm.

207 Helium and CO gases are supplied to the buffer gas cell from their respective bottles, with the
208 flow rates of both gases controlled by flowmeters (MCE-20SCCM-D-6MMCOMP for helium
209 and MCE-1SCCM-D-6MMCOMP for CO, by Alicat). The helium line passes through a cooling
210 cell soldered to the 4-K stage of the cryostat. The cold helium is injected into the buffer cell
211 via a stainless steel capillary tube with an outer diameter of 3.2 mm, as depicted in Fig. 2. The

212 CO gas is introduced from the back end of the cell through a 3.2-mm-outer-diameter copper
 213 capillary tube. This tube is thermally isolated from the buffer cell by a PEEK piece, and cartridge
 214 heaters are used to keep the CO line at 70 K by a PID controller to prevent freezing. This heating
 215 arrangement is illustrated in Fig. 2. Under standard pressure, CO liquefy at 81.15 K and freezes
 216 at 74.15 K.

217 3.2. Optical transitions, detection, and the laser system

Fig. 3. Scheme of the molecular beam and detection system.

218 To detect CO molecules emerging from the buffer cell, we first excite them to a metastable triplet
 219 state with a pulsed laser. 1 mJ of light at 206 nm saturates the spin-forbidden transition $a^3\Pi_1(v = 0, J = 1) \leftarrow X^1\Sigma^+(v = 0)$. The $a^3\Pi_1(v = 0, J = 1)$ has a lifetime of 2.63 ms. [20] Then,
 220 we detect their phosphorescence on a photo-multiplier tube (PMT) (9813BQ, ET Enterprises),
 221 positioned approximately 24.5 cm downstream from the excitation region. It has an efficiency of
 222 30% at 206 nm and it is mounted behind a quartz window with a transmission of 90% at 206 nm.
 223 The PMT is 117 mm from the axis of the molecular beam and has an effective entrance aperture
 224 of 35 mm in diameter. Such geometry allows for the collection of phosphorescence signal under
 225 0.07 sr. All together these parameters yield a total detection efficiency of 0.135%. We show a
 226 scheme of this setup in Figure 3. We acquire the phosphorescence signal with 13 μ s resolution.
 227 For the range of velocities studied in this work (100–250 m/s), this set of parameters yields a
 228 velocity resolution of about ± 10 m/s and detection efficiency is independent on velocity in first
 229 approximation. A first aperture in the 40-K shield reduce the divergence of the beam, but the field
 230 of view of the PMT further reduce the portion of the beam that is detected, yielding an overall
 231 divergence of 0.012 sr. This value is large but we believe that it is a useful measure because with
 232 high-power lasers one can decelerate and transverse-cool beams with such characteristics.
 233

234 The electronic ground state $X^1\Sigma^+$ is best described in Hund's case (b), where the rotational
 235 states are fully characterized by the rotational quantum number N . The parity of the rotational
 236 states follows $(-1)^N$. In contrast, the rotational structure of the electronically excited state $a^3\Pi_1$
 237 is described by the total angular momentum quantum number J . We characterized the buffer gas
 238 cell by exciting the CO molecules from the rotational levels $N = 0$ to the lower component of the
 239 Λ doublet in the $a^3\Pi_1 (J = 1)$ state. Only for the data shown in Figure 8, we excite molecules
 240 also from the $N = 1$ level to the upper component of the Λ doublet in the $a^3\Pi_1 (J = 1)$ state. A

241 more detailed description of the energy levels can be found in Ref [21].

242 We employed a laser system similar to that described in Ref [22], which generates a pulsed
243 beam with an energy of approximately 1 mJ at 206 nm, a repetition rate of 10 Hz, a pulse duration
244 of around 6 ns and a linewidth of approximately 200 MHz.

245 4. Results and discussions

Fig. 4. Arrival time of CO molecules in front of the PMT with 1 SCCM of CO, and 0 and 12, 16, 20 SCCM of helium, a 3-cm cell length and 5-mm aperture, solid lines. The dashed lines are the fit of a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution to the data. On top, the arrival time is converted into the correspondent molecular velocity.

246 Figure 4 shows the phosphorescence signal detected by the PMT, both in the presence and
247 absence of helium flow in the cell. We correct for the exponential decay of the population in the
248 excited states and take the overall detection efficiency into account to calculate the number of
249 molecules/(s sr) that have been prepared by the laser in a single quantum state.

250 Knowing the CO excitation time and the phosphorescence time, and the distance between
251 excitation laser and PMT, we calculate the velocity of the molecular beam, shown on the horizontal
252 axis on top of the graph. The shift in the overall profile and in the forward velocity in dependence
253 of the helium flow clearly indicate the cooling effect on CO. We attribute this effect to the
254 thermalization of CO molecules within the buffer cell. Collisions with He atoms might transfer
255 part of the metastable population to the lower rotational states of the $\Omega = 0$ manifold on the $a^3\Pi$
256 state. However, the lifetime of those states are about two orders of magnitude longer than from
257 the $\Omega = 1$ states. Therefore, we consider their contribution to the observed signal to be negligible.

258 Fitting the time of flight profiles in Figure 4 to a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution yields
259 temperatures of 69.2 ± 0.1 K and 6.9 ± 0.2 K for helium flow rates of 0 and 20 SCCM, respectively.
260 Two different effects are responsible for the observed data. Collisions with helium lower the CO

Fig. 5. Integrated phosphorescence signal in dependence on He flow rate, for all aperture diameters and cell lengths. In all cases, larger He flow yields larger CO signal.

261 velocity from the over 250 m/s expected for CO at around 70 K (temperature of the CO line) to
 262 below 150 m/s. However, by further increasing the He flow, we increase the Reynolds number
 263 and slightly accelerate CO molecules.

264 Figure 5 shows the CO phosphorescence signal in dependence on the He flow rate, for all
 265 source configurations. We see a monotonic signal increase with increasing flow, up to 20 SCCM,
 266 which is the limit of our He flowmeter. The same is true for the CO flow rate, which is limited to
 267 1 SCCM by the CO flowmeter. Therefore, all data shown in the following are measured with 1
 268 SCCM of CO and 20 SCCM of He.

269 We test Eq. (6) by measuring the phosphorescence signal in dependence on the cell length for
 270 various nozzle sizes, Figure 6. A shorter cell minimizes the probability of diffusion to the walls
 271 and thus increases the extraction efficiency, γ . Measured data show a qualitative agreement with
 272 theory. However, although we do not expect significant dependence on the nozzle sizes, we know
 273 from the literature that lower output is expected when the nozzle is too small, see Ref. [14]. This
 274 is in fact what we observe with a nozzle diameter of 3 mm.

275 We then investigate the dependency of the forward velocity on the nozzle diameter, which
 276 influences the Reynolds number characterizing the flow at the source exit. Data are shown in
 277 Figure 7. We fit a Maxwell-Boltzmann curve to the recorded phosphorescence signal and extract
 278 a peak forward velocity. Although we observe an overall velocity reduction upon nozzle diameter
 279 enlargement, we also see large difference depending on cell length. With longer cells, CO
 280 molecules undergo more collisions and are thus more likely to diffuse to the walls. Therefore, we

Fig. 6. Phosphorescence signal in dependence on cell length for various nozzle diameters.

281 believe that faster molecules that spend a shorter time in the cell have a larger chance of leaving
 282 the cell through the nozzle. Those faster molecules thus push the observed velocity distribution
 283 in the beam toward a larger average speed for 4 and 5-cm cell length.

284 With 5-mm aperture and 2-cm length of the cell, the peak of the measured signal is about
 285 2.5×10^{14} molecules/(s sr). We form a beam that can be used as a precursor for laser cooling,
 286 as discussed above, of about 3×10^{12} molecules/s. This can be compared with the incoming
 287 CO flow of 1 SCCM, or 4.5×10^{17} molecules/s, yielding an overall efficiency of the buffer gas
 288 cooling of about 10^{-5} , from the bottle to the beam.

289 Finally, we compare signal from $N = 0$ and $N = 1$ for various He flow rates. Integrated
 290 phosphorescence signal from the $a^3\Pi$ state is plotted in dependence on He flow in Fig 8. The
 291 observed signal ratio of $N = 0$ to $N = 1$ is roughly 9:1. This is somehow surprising. In $N = 1$
 292 there are 3 times as many states as in $N = 0$; but selection rules should not allow excitation of
 293 $M = 0$ in $N = 1$. Therefore, considering the energy difference of CO in the ground state between
 294 the two rotational states and a temperature of 4 K, we expect the ratio of $N = 0$ to $N = 1$
 295 to be about 2:1. It is known that rotational thermalisation inside the cell with the buffer gas can
 296 be modeled in a satisfactory way. [23] So, in order to account for the observed 9:1 ratio, we
 297 should assume a temperature inside the cell below 2 K, against a measured temperature at the cell
 298 surface of 3.7 K. According to the cryostat producer, Cryomech, the 2.7 W of cooling capacity of
 299 the cryostat at 4.2 K should be sufficient to liquefy the helium that passes through the cooling coil
 300 mounted on the cryostat head. Thus, He evaporating inside the cell would lower the temperature,

Fig. 7. Peak forward velocity in dependence on nozzle diameter for various cell lengths.

301 but the system could be far away from equilibrium and not easy to measure directly. Therefore,
 302 at present, we cannot give a definite explanation of the ratio of the two rotational states.

Fig. 8. Phosphorescence signal for N=0 and N=1, Cell length 3 cm and 5 mm aperture.

303 **5. Conclusion**

304 In this work, we have developed and characterized a cryogenic buffer gas cell source for the
305 formation of continuous molecular beams. Our combined theoretical description and experimental
306 observations contribute to the growing understanding of molecular beam formation using a buffer
307 gas cell. By systematically varying the buffer gas flow, the length of the cooling region, and
308 the diameter of the nozzle, our research demonstrates the impact of these parameters on key
309 properties of the molecular beam; specifically, on cooling efficiency, molecular beam extraction,
310 and forward velocity.

311 A key finding of this study is that CO molecules experience significant translational cooling,
312 with their temperature reduced from 78 K to 7 K at optimal helium flow rates. The forward
313 velocity of the CO molecules is influenced by the Reynolds number, while a shorter cell length
314 enhances molecular extraction by minimizing losses due to diffusion to the walls. Additionally, a
315 nozzle size above 3 mm provides efficient beam flux.

316 The source studied here can be adapted for a wide range of molecular species, providing
317 a foundational understanding of buffer gas cell operation. These findings have important
318 implications for the production of efficient cold molecular beam sources and their subsequent
319 applications in precision measurements and cold molecular experiments.

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327 6. References

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